

PSYCHOLOGY OF PATIENTS IN EPILEPSY

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Abstract: In this article, we will consider the psychology of patients with epilepsy, which is considered one of the most pressing issues in the fields of medicine and psychology today.

Keywords: epilepsy, patient psychology, brain attack, medical-social problem, behavior change, psychiatric supervision.

Epilepsy is one of the most widespread diseases of the nervous system and has become a major medical and social problem. Epilepsy is a chronic disease of the brain with seizures, manifested by movement, sensation, vegetative and psycho-emotional disorders. The prevalence of epilepsy among the population is 7-10 cases per 1000 people. Since the disease has multiple etiologies, it can occur at different ages, but 75% of epilepsy begins before the age of 20. The prevalence of the disease is almost the same in men and women. According to experts, mental disorders are observed in at least 30% of patients with epilepsy.

It is known from history that great people such as Socrates, Plato, Julius Caesar, Joan of Arc, Van Gogh, Napoleon, F. Dostoevsky suffered from epilepsy. That's why some experts say that only strong thinkers suffer from epilepsy, while others believe that seizures trigger the bud of talent in a person. It is difficult to fully agree with these opinions, but in some patients with epilepsy, strong signs of talent can be found. [1, 97]

For example, in our practice, we have met a young man who knows the Quran and Hadith by heart, strong artists, poets and mathematicians. Among such patients, we have observed those who come up with wise phrases that surprise people, and those

who are full of wisdom. It will be useful if they are written in the side notebooks of doctors. We observed an increase in sensitivity and perception in a patient with frequent seizures. However, in most patients with epilepsy, if it is not stopped during seizures, it causes severe mental disorders, and the mind becomes weak. The earlier the seizures start, the earlier mental disorders can develop. However, severe mental disorders are not observed in all types of epilepsy. [2, 181]

Epilepsy is characterized by mental disorders accompanied by changes in the patient's behavior. Unlike other mental disorders, in epilepsy, the patient's personality changes are characterized by their uniqueness, as a result of which the phrase "epileptic behavior" appeared in medical practice. Such patients are very stubborn, stubborn, impatient, easily upset, change their mood quickly, get involved in trivial matters, start quarrels, talk small and have a temper. Of course, the patient may have these symptoms in different ways, and the severity of the symptoms depends on the frequency of seizures, the type of epilepsy and the type of treatment. A patient who is in a good mood can suddenly change and start insulting loved ones with rude words. Such a situation occurs when he cannot find something, when someone interferes with his work and points out his mistake, when he expresses an opinion contrary to his opinion, etc. [4, 169]

Then the patient quickly picks up quarrels and fights, sometimes a small quarrel escalates to the level of affect, and the patient can injure himself or others. Therefore, the letter should send such patients under the supervision of a psychiatrist. Therefore, a patient with epilepsy accompanied by sudden changes in behavior should be treated under the supervision of a psychiatrist. [7, 89]

In epilepsy, mental, emotional and thinking disorders develop strongly in the last stages of the disease, and this is obvious! is noticeable. In such patients, seizures may have completely stopped. That is why psychiatrists say that mental disorders are responsible for seizures in the last stages of epilepsy.

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